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SWOT Analysis

Distributed Acoustic Sensing

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1. Acronyms

Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS)

Controlled Source Electromagnetics (CSEM)

Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS)

Distributed Strain Sensing (DSS)

Distributed Temperature Sensing (DTS)

Life-Of-Field Systems (LOFS)

Machine Learning (ML)

Measurement, Monitoring, and Verification (MMV)

Ocean Bottom Cable (OBC)

Ocean Bottom Nodes (OBN)

Permanent Reservoir Monitoring (PRM)

Signal-To-Noise Ratio (SNR)

Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT)

Technology Readiness Level (TRL)

Vertical Seismic Profiling (VSP)

2. Introduction

The MoTech project, funded by Empowered Startups, Hemisfério Envolvente, and the European project PilotSTRATEGY, is dedicated to advancing the understanding of state-of-the-art monitoring technologies for offshore CO₂ storage. Led by the Department of Geosciences of the University of Évora in collaboration with experts from the oil and gas industry, the project focuses on identifying effective, innovative, and cost-efficient monitoring strategies for CO₂ storage in geological sites. Central to its objectives is the evaluation of technologies that can ensure the safety, integrity, and long-term containment of injected CO₂, particularly in offshore settings like the pilot site located near Figueira da Foz, Portugal.

Within this scope and following the work performed in previous deliverables of the MoTech project, Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) emerges as a promising monitoring solution (Gorshkov et al., 2022). DAS converts standard fibre-optic cables into continuous acoustic sensors capable of capturing seismic and vibrational signals along their entire length. This approach enables real-time, spatially dense monitoring of subsurface dynamics without the need for extensive sensor deployments. By reusing the existing fibre infrastructure, such as submarine telecommunications cables or borehole fibres, DAS may offer a potentially cost-effective and scalable alternative to conventional time-lapse seismic surveys.

The purpose of this analysis is to critically assess the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT) associated with deploying DAS technology in the context of offshore carbon capture and storage. In doing so, it aims to support the development of integrated monitoring strategies that balance technical performance, environmental responsibility, and economic feasibility, while contributing to the long-term viability of CCS as a climate mitigation solution.

3. Strengths

3.1 High sensitivity to small changes

The Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) technology works by detecting light scattering resulting from small fluctuations in the fibre's refractive index (Lindsey & Martin, 2021). According to DNV (2024), monitoring methods such as time-lapse (4D) seismic and gravity surveys exhibit a high degree of sensitivity to subtle variations in reservoir pressure and saturation. These technologies facilitate the accurate detection of CO₂ plume migration, seal integrity breaches, and geomechanical deformation, delivering fine spatial and temporal resolution critical for assessing containment and ensuring model conformance. DAS systems, in particular, offer the unique advantage of capturing minute changes in strain and acoustic signals along the fibre, supporting high-resolution, real-time identification of key subsurface behaviours essential to safe and reliable offshore CO₂ storage operations.

3.2 Real-time data collection

Strain measurements along the fibre-optic cable are captured thousands of times per second, enabling continuous, high-frequency monitoring. DAS transforms existing or purpose-installed optical fibres into densely distributed seismic sensor arrays, offering near real-time surveillance of subsurface conditions. This facilitates the prompt identification of anomalies during both the injection and post-injection phases, significantly improving risk mitigation and operational responsiveness (Sidenko et al., 2022). Notably, the spatial resolution achieved with DAS is typically 20 times higher than that of traditional geophone-based VSP, and data acquisition is completed within minutes, in contrast to the hours often required by conventional wireline VSP systems with limited geophone deployments (DNV, 2024).

3.3 Lower long-run costs

While initial deployment costs for DAS can be substantial, DNV (2024) notes that Permanent Reservoir Monitoring (PRM) systems, such as Life-of-Field Systems

(LOFS), become increasingly cost-effective over time when compared to repeated active seismic campaigns.

For 2D DAS VSP installations, costs are typically around 500,000 € per well when using a rig-based seismic source, with data processing expenses ranging between 10,000 and 100,000 € per survey (DNV, 2024). In contrast, 3D or 4D DAS campaigns involve higher costs, with installation expenditures ranging from 100,000 to over 1 million € for each repeated 3D VSP acquisition (DNV, 2024). Operationally, DAS offers logistical advantages, a 2 × 2 km area surrounding an observation well can typically be surveyed within two days, at an estimated vessel day rate of approximately 100,000 €. Including mobilisation and sailing time, the initial survey is expected to cost around 1 million €, with subsequent surveys estimated at about half that amount, reserving costs to the mobilisation/sailing. For comparison, standard seismic surveys generally cost between 100,000 and 1 million €, sometimes even surpassing it, with unit costs ranging from 100 to 300 € per km², although, large-scale surveys covering thousands of km² have been processed efficiently at costs below 100 € per km² (DNV, 2024).

3.4 Minimal environmental disturbance

DAS is increasingly recognised for its ability to offer non-invasive, low-impact monitoring across a wide range of CCS applications. Unlike conventional seismic monitoring systems, which often require extensive field operations, heavy equipment, and repeated physical interventions, DAS systems rely on fibre-optic cables that can be permanently installed in wells or repurposed from existing infrastructure, such as submarine communication cables.

The CCS White Paper (Silixa, 2022) highlights that DAS enables *"long-term, on-demand, and cost-effective seismic monitoring solutions"* without the need for well re-entry or additional surface disturbance. It specifically notes DAS's *"minimal environmental impact"*, especially in the context of the Aquistore site (Canada), where fibres have been used for years without invasive redeployments.

The latter is also supported by Jenkins (2020) by describing DAS as facilitating "*continuous and unobtrusive monitoring*", allowing for the operation of permanent sources and receivers with minimal field intervention. This makes it especially attractive for risk-based monitoring frameworks that prioritise less impacts and logistical minimalism.

Further reinforcement comes from Shao et al. (2025), who underline that DAS systems can be deployed "*non-invasively and permanently in a single deployment*", greatly reducing the operational footprint and associated risks of traditional seismic instrumentation. The document stresses the suitability of DAS for monitoring in sensitive or logistically constrained environments such as carbon storage reservoirs, salt domes, and glacial formations.

In offshore contexts, the Otway Stage 3 project (Australia), explicitly aims to develop continuous low-cost and low-environmental footprint solutions using fibre-optic DAS systems. These deployments avoid seafloor disturbances typically associated with OBC systems and eliminate the need for repeated vessel operations.

4. Weaknesses

4.1 High setup and installation costs

Installation costs for DAS arrays typically cost about 500,000 € per well, with additional expenses for mobilisation and data processing. In the case of large-scale 3D or 4D DAS-enabled VSP surveys it can range from 100,000 up to 1 million € (DNV, 2024). While DAS offers clear long-term cost efficiencies, the upfront capital investment remains considerable, particularly for offshore applications requiring complex deployment logistics. An additional drawback of DAS technology is the vulnerability to suffer damages during installation of tubing or casing which may result in higher installation costs (DNV, 2024).

4.2 Generation of large, complex datasets

DAS systems generate high-density, continuous spatiotemporal data, often recorded at sub-metre resolution and kilohertz sampling rates. While this facilitates fine-scale monitoring of subsurface dynamics, it also results in enormous volumes of raw data. Processing such data requires advanced storage infrastructure, high-performance computing resources, and specialised interpretation tools, a particular challenge in offshore environments where data transmission bandwidth is often constrained (DNV, 2024). Moreover, as noted by Gorshkov et al. (2022), DAS datasets typically integrate both temporal and frequency-domain components over large spatial extents, rendering standard signal processing techniques inadequate without dedicated algorithms and computational frameworks.

4.3 Dependence on high-quality training data for advanced interpretation

When DAS is combined with ML or automated anomaly detection, the performance of these models is heavily dependent on the availability of reliable, high-resolution baseline datasets. Without sufficient historical or labelled data, model interpretability is often significantly compromised. As highlighted by Ganesh et al. (2022), advanced ML applications such as leakage detection or stress-state

evaluation require rich, scenario-specific datasets to function effectively. This challenge is higher in offshore CCS contexts, where real-world data are both scarce and costly to acquire, and where site-specific variability further complicates data transferability. Consequently, many current studies continue to rely on synthetic datasets, which increases the risk of model overfitting and limits the practical deployment of these tools in operational settings.

4.4 Limited technological maturity in offshore CCS contexts

Although DAS has demonstrated reliability in oil and gas operations, its deployment in offshore CCS monitoring, particularly within long-term permanent monitoring frameworks, remains relatively immature. Compared to conventional geophysical methods, there are fewer large-scale implementations focused specifically on CO₂ storage. As Jenkins (2020) points out, while DAS has shown considerable promise in controlled environments and upstream energy sectors, its application to offshore CO₂ storage is still largely confined to pilot-scale trials and experimental deployments, with limited examples of validated, long-duration field use. Likewise, DAS is classified with a Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of 6, which still considers the technology as “innovative” and not fully embedded within the mainstream MMV toolkit adopted by most CCS projects and regulatory bodies (DNV, 2024).

4.5 Restricted sensing range

While DAS systems can, in theory, monitor over tens of kilometres along a fibre, their effective sensing range for high-resolution seismic monitoring, namely in borehole applications relevant to CCS, is often significantly more limited (Dean et al., 2016). Several factors constrain this range, including optical signal attenuation, signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) degradation with depth and offset, and the need for strong acoustic coupling between the fibre and the geological formation.

The DNV (2024) report acknowledges that DAS performance in wellbores is largely constrained to the vicinity of the wellbore, noting that “it is not possible to record at a long distance from the wellbore when high velocity contrasts prevent transmission of seismic energy” (DNV, 2024). A practical rule of thumb places the

functional sensing limit at around 800 - 1000m, though this can vary depending on geology and installation method (for example: tubing vs cemented fibres).

Literature supports the existence of these constraints. Daley et al. (2013) reported that DAS on tubing at the Citronelle site (Alabama), an onshore project, produced reliable SNR down to a radial distance of approximately 1.6km from the borehole, although conventional geophones maintained good performance out to 2.1km. In contrast, DAS did not provide usable image quality at these distances. Similar limitations were noted at the Otway site (Australia), where the recorded signal was promising but ultimately insufficient for effective imaging. Ajo-Franklin et al. (2013) also observed that DAS systems in borehole deployments tend to perform most reliably within a radial distance of about 1km from the well, due to a combination of acoustic attenuation and optical backscatter limitations. At Ketzin (Germany), fibres that were partially cemented onto the casing at depths of up to 700m initially produced data of promising yet limited quality, which was common at the time. It was only later, in the study by Götz et al. (2018), that a successful DAS-VSP image was acquired at the site demonstrating that cemented coupling significantly enhances DAS sensitivity and imaging performance, even in relatively shallow formations.

At Aquistore (Canada), a cemented fibre yielded usable data to ~2.5 - 3.0km depth, with Harris et al. (2016) showing that DAS-VSP could detect subtle changes associated with CO₂ injection. Despite these advances, these examples also show the complex site-specific engineering required for DAS to perform comparably to geophones, especially in offshore contexts where there are long offsets and more challenging environments.

5. Opportunities

5.1 Adaptability to varied geological and operational scenarios

DAS systems are highly adaptable, capable of being deployed in both existing and new wells using either tubing-conveyed or cemented fibres. This flexibility makes DAS suitable for a broad range of offshore CCS environments, including depleted hydrocarbon fields, deep saline aquifers, and geologically complex reservoirs. Installations can be tailored to project requirements, with retrievable or permanent configurations, enabling both cost control and reusability (DNV, 2024; Silixa Ltd, 2022). DAS's passive nature and compatibility with existing infrastructure allow it to be seamlessly integrated into a variety of regulatory and risk-based monitoring frameworks. As noted in Jenkins (2020), DAS is agnostic to the stored fluid type, supporting monitoring whether the site involves CO₂, brine, or gas transitions. This technological neutrality, combined with its modular installation options, makes DAS well-suited for deployment across offshore CCS sites that differ in depth, lithology, and operational phase. Furthermore, as demonstrated in Shell's MMV strategies (Dean, 2020; Dean et al., 2020), DAS can serve a key role across the entire project lifecycle, from pre-injection baseline surveys to active injection and post-closure verification, supporting fit-for-purpose, risk-informed monitoring that is both scalable and repeatable.

In addition to its technical versatility, DAS presents a strong commercial opportunity in light of the accelerating global deployment of CCS technologies. As governments and industries scale up carbon storage to meet net-zero targets, the demand for cost-effective, reliable monitoring systems is increasing. DAS offers a compelling value proposition by reducing operational costs through passive monitoring, lowering the need for frequent well interventions, and enabling multi-well or even reservoir-scale observation using a single interrogator unit. These features align well with market needs for financially viable MMV strategies, especially in emerging CCS hubs where cost remains a key barrier. As such, DAS is

not only a flexible and technically robust solution, but also a commercially strategic asset in the rapidly evolving CCS landscape.

5.2 Integration with complementary technologies

DAS offers strong potential for integration with both established and emerging monitoring technologies, creating synergies that enhance spatial and temporal resolution across subsurface domains. Commonly paired with tools such as Distributed Temperature Sensing (DTS), Distributed Strain Sensing (DSS), Ocean Bottom Nodes (OBN), Controlled Source Electromagnetics (CSEM), and Time-Lapse (4D) Seismic, DAS contributes to the formation of multi-modal datasets capable of capturing diverse subsurface behaviours, from CO₂ plume migration to geomechanical stress evolution (DNV, 2024).

For example, coupling DAS with DTS enables the simultaneous detection of acoustic and thermal anomalies, which is especially useful for identifying thermal breakthroughs and interpreting thermally-driven flow dynamics – a capability of growing relevance in complex offshore reservoirs (DNV, 2024).

In parallel, the integration of DAS with machine learning (ML) and data fusion models is expanding rapidly. Studies by Ganesh et al. (2022) and Gorshkov et al. (2022) demonstrate how ML algorithms can isolate weak signals, such as those generated by microseismic events or early leakage, which may otherwise go undetected. These AI-enhanced workflows are particularly valuable in offshore CCS settings, where continuous, high-frequency anomaly detection can offer a predictive edge in risk mitigation and system responsiveness. As emphasised in by Silixa Ltd (2022), permanent fibre installations combining DAS and DTS can enable autonomous, low-impact monitoring architectures capable of operating with minimal human intervention, making them ideal for the long-term, regulated monitoring required in CCS projects.

5.3 Enhanced predictive accuracy and conformance assessment

The high spatial and temporal resolution of DAS enables detailed observation of dynamic subsurface processes such as pressure front advancement, CO₂ plume migration, and fault activation in near real time. This fine-scale monitoring capability supports the calibration and continuous validation of geomechanical and flow models, enhancing the predictive accuracy of simulations used in CCS risk assessments (Harris et al., 2016; Ganesh et al., 2022).

When integrated with baseline surveys and geophysical characterisation, DAS facilitates the identification of key phenomena including stress accumulation, reservoir deformation, and caprock integrity risks. Additionally, DAS-based strain profiling has proven useful for the early detection of subsurface anomalies, enabling scenario-based forecasting and proactive mitigation planning (Harris et al., 2016; Ganesh et al., 2022).

The Global CCS Institute (2024) emphasises that DAS-generated high-frequency datasets are instrumental for adaptive monitoring protocols, in which model parameters are iteratively updated to reduce uncertainty and optimise operational strategies. In this regard, DAS emerges as a cornerstone technology for the development of "smart CCS" systems, supporting conformance assessment and injection optimisation across both regulated frameworks and commercial-scale deployments.

5.4 Potential to improve long-term cost-effectiveness

Although initial installation costs for DAS can be significant, particularly when configured for 3D/4D seismic or embedded in cemented casing completions, its long-term economic value lies in its capacity for repeatable, low-intervention monitoring. Once deployed, DAS fibres can remain in situ for decades, either in the ocean bottom or cemented down the borehole, supporting LOFS and baseline-to-post-closure monitoring without the need for re-entry or additional downhole mobilisation (DNV, 2024). This permanence and passive operability enable cost

savings through reduced vessel dependency, lower operational risk, and enhanced survey repeatability. As highlighted by the Global CCS Institute (2024), DAS is particularly well-suited to the emerging paradigm of networked CO₂ storage hubs, where minimising intervention frequency and personnel deployment is paramount. Furthermore, case studies such as Shell's Quest CCS project (Canada) demonstrate that repeated DAS-enabled Vertical Seismic Profiling can serve as a cost-effective alternative to surface seismic for verifying containment and conformance during early injection phases. In such deployments, DAS provided fit-for-purpose imaging with fewer resources, and at a fraction of the cost of traditional methods. With the additional advantage of automation potential and remote analytics, DAS is increasingly positioned as a cost-optimised solution for CCS monitoring across the full lifecycle, supporting not only regulatory compliance but also commercial viability over multi-decade timeframes (Silixa Ltd, 2022; DNV, 2024; GCCSI, 2024).

6. Threats

6.1 Competition from more mature technologies

DAS still competes with established seismic and geophysical methods such as conventional VSP using geophones, OBN, and 4D Surface Seismic. These technologies benefit from decades of operational maturity, proven imaging resolution, and regulatory familiarity, making them the default in conservative offshore monitoring settings. DAS, in contrast, remains relatively novel, with adoption typically limited to pilot projects or as a complementary tool rather than a primary method (DNV, 2024; Daley et al., 2013). In field comparisons, geophones demonstrated superior depth penetration and imaging quality, with DAS producing insufficient imaging at depths beyond 1.6–2.1km in some CCS trials (Daley et al., 2013; Jenkins, 2020).

6.2 Sensitivity to environmental and operational noise

Despite its high resolution, DAS is highly sensitive to ambient and operational noise, including flow-induced vibrations, drilling activity, and surface infrastructure like platforms and ships. In offshore CCS environments, such noise can obscure weak seismic or acoustic signals, reducing signal-to-noise ratios and undermining detection accuracy for microseismic events or subtle plume migration (DNV, 2024; Harris et al., 2016). Recent offshore testing also confirms that environmental coupling issues and interference become particularly significant at large offsets or in shallow installations (Gorshkov et al., 2022).

6.3 Technological obsolescence risk

The rapid evolution of fibre-optic materials, signal processing algorithms, and machine learning platforms risks making today's DAS deployments obsolete within a few years. This poses a particular threat for long-duration CCS projects, which depend on stable, validated monitoring architectures over decades (DNV, 2024). Ageing fibres are also vulnerable to hydrogen darkening, a process in which hydrogen molecules diffuse into the glass and form light-absorbing hydroxyl groups

that degrade optical signal transmission, as well as pressure cycling and thermal degradation, especially in high-salinity or corrosive borehole environments (Morana et al., 2024; Matsuda et al., 2024; Miele et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2024). While new coatings and laser technologies offer improved resilience (GCCSI, 2024), legacy DAS systems may be incompatible with future analytics platforms, complicating upgrades and jeopardising data continuity (Park et al., 2019; Silixa Ltd, 2022).

6.4 Cybersecurity vulnerabilities in digital infrastructure

As DAS transitions into cloud-connected, remotely managed systems, it becomes increasingly vulnerable to cyber threats. A breach in DAS telemetry or control infrastructure could compromise regulatory reporting, trigger false alarms, or result in operational shutdowns. The sheer volume of DAS data (often several terabytes per survey) exacerbates the risk, demanding robust encryption, data authentication, and redundant edge computing solutions (Gorshkov et al., 2022; GCCSI, 2024). As noted in recent digitalisation frameworks, cybersecurity for DAS is not yet a standardised field, making it a critical gap in large-scale offshore CCS deployment strategies (DNV, 2024).

7. Final remarks

With this report, the team of the University of Évora aimed to provide a SWOT analysis of the DAS technology, which was identified as an emergent and cost-effective solution to assist monitoring of CO₂ injection and storage in geological reservoirs. It was challenging to pick up one of the available options identified in previous MoTech project deliverables since, as mentioned above in the opportunities section, the integration and combination of different technologies certainly contributes to reduce uncertainties and to improve the risk management of CCS projects. A summary of the conclusions included in this report is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Graphical representation of the SWOT analysis.

8. References

Ajo-Franklin, J., Peterson, J., Doetsch, J., & Daley, T. (2013). High-resolution characterization of a CO₂ plume using crosswell seismic tomography: Cranfield, MS, USA. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, 18, 497–509. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2012.12.018>

Chen, S., You, H., Xu, J., Wei, M., Xu, T., & Wang, H. (2024). Leakage monitoring of carbon dioxide injection well string using distributed optical fiber sensor. *Petroleum Research*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ptlrs.2024.08.003>

Daley, T. M., Freifeld, B. M., Ajo-Franklin, J. B., Dou, S., Pevzner, R., Shulakova, V., & White, D. (2013). Field testing of fibre-optic distributed acoustic sensing (DAS) for subsurface seismic monitoring. *The Leading Edge*, 32(6), 699–706. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1190/tle32060699.1>

Dean, M. (2020). Offshore monitoring for CCS: Safe and effective monitoring at lower costs. Presented at the 4th International Workshop on Offshore Geologic CO₂ Storage, Bergen, Norway. Shell Global Solutions International B.V. URL: <https://stemm-ccs.eu/sites/stemm-ccs/files/documents/1545%20Marcella%20Dean%20Offshore%20monitoring%20for%20CCS-safe%20and%20effective%20monitoring%20at%20lower%20costs.pdf>

Dean, M., Blackford, J., Connelly, D., & Hines, R. (2020). Insights and guidance for offshore CO₂ storage monitoring based on the QICS, ETI MMV, and STEMM-CCS projects. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, 100, 103120. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2020.103120>

Dean, T., Brice, T., Hartog, A., Kragh, E., Molteni, D., & O'Connell, K. (2016). Distributed vibration sensing for seismic acquisition. *The Leading Edge*, 35(7), 600–604. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1190/tle35070600.1>

DNV. (2024). KEM-27: Technical Review of Monitoring Solutions for CCS. KEM Programme. URL: https://kemprogramma.nl/file/download/ad9b1070-460b-4600-a689-ddbc0d4c22df/kem27_dnv_final_report_29052024_external.pdf

Ganesh, P., Tertyshnikov, K., Yavuz, S., & Pevzner, R. (2022). DAS data simulation and ML-based event classification for seismic monitoring in CO₂ storage. *Scientific Reports*, 12(1), 19527. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-24163-3>

Global CCS Institute. (2024). Global Status of CCS 2024: CCS accelerating to net zero. URL: <https://www.globalccsinstitute.com/resources/global-status-report/>

Gorshkov, A., Pevzner, R., Tertyshnikov, K., & Yavuz, S. (2022). DAS-based microseismic detection and localisation using convolutional neural networks. *Scientific Reports*, 12, 3893. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-07894-1>

Götz, J., Lüth, S., Henniges, J., & Reinsch, T. (2018). Vertical seismic profiling using a daisy-chained deployment of fibre-optic cables in four wells simultaneously – Case study at the Ketzin carbon dioxide storage site. *Geophysical Prospecting*, 66(6), 1201–1214. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2478.12638>

Harris, K., White, D., Melanson, D., Samson, C., & Daley, T. M. (2016). Feasibility of time-lapse VSP monitoring at the Aquistore CO₂ storage site using a distributed sensing system. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, 50, 248–260. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2016.04.016>

Jenkins, C. R. (2020). Advances in CO₂ storage monitoring with distributed acoustic sensing (DAS). *Geophysics*, 85(5), WA99–WA110. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1190/geo2019-0362.1>

Lindsey, N. J., & Martin, E. R. (2021). Fiber-Optic seismology. *Annual Review of Earth and Planetary Sciences*, 49(1), 309–336. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-earth-072420-065213>

Matsuda, T., Kitaoka, S., Nakahira, K., Ito, T., Kato, T., & Kasahara, J. (2023). Evaluation of in-situ optical loss of polyimide-coated optical fiber under hydrothermal environments. *Optical Fiber Technology*, 82, 103582. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yofte.2023.103582>

Miele, P., Snead, K., Zakhireh, N., Homa, D., Pickrell, G., & Risch, B. G. (2020). Optical fiber reliability in harsh environments. In *Int. Wire & Cable Symp.* URL: [\(PDF\) Optical Fiber Reliability in Harsh Environments](#)

Morana, A., Roche, M., Marin, E., Boukenter, A., Ouerdane, Y., & Girard, S. (2024). Influence of hydrogen on the Radiation-Induced attenuation of ge-doped optical fibers. *IEEE Transactions on Nuclear Science*, 71(4), 752–758. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/tns.2024.3359859>

Park, J., Lee, J., & Kim, S. (2019). Long-term reliability of fibre-optic sensors in harsh environments. *Sensors*, 19(5), 1234. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/s19051234>

Shao, L., Zhang, J., Chen, X., Xu, D., Gu, H., Mu, Q., Yu, F., Liu, S., Shi, X., Sun, J., Huang, Z., Yang, X., Zhang, H., Ma, Y., Lu, H., Liu, C., & Yu, C. (2025). Artificial intelligence-driven distributed acoustic sensing technology and engineering application. *PhotoniX*, 6(1). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43074-025-00160-z>

Sidenko, E., Tertyshnikov, K., Gurevich, B., & Pevzner, R. (2022). DAS signature of reservoir pressure changes caused by a CO₂ injection: Experience from the CO₂CRC Otway Project. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, 119, 103735. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2022.103735>

Silixa Ltd. (2022). Carbon Capture and Storage Monitoring with Distributed Fibre Optic Sensing. URL: https://silixa.com/wp-content/uploads/CCUS_White_Paper_October_2022.pdf